

Introduction

General information about the region

The study area encompasses region of Victoria Lake and 3 adjoining countries: Tanzania, Kenya and Uganda. Lake Victoria is the second largest fresh water body on the Earth with unique environment giving origin of the Nile waters. Lake Victoria occupies a shallow depression in the East African Plateau. Being 68,800 square kilometres, Lake Victoria is Africa's largest lake and largest tropical land. The lake only received waters from precipitation, and has the only outflow river – White Nile. The maximum depth of the lake is 84metres and an average depth is 20 metres, so that it is a shallow water reservoir. The Victoria lake supports largest inland fishery in Africa.

Specific objectives and aims

Besides unique environment, Victoria lake plays an important role in the economy of the surrounding countries supporting 25 million people through lake fish catchment reaching up to 90-270\$ per capita per annum. Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda control 6%, 49% and 45% of the lake surface, respectively. Thus, the lake catchment provides for the livelihood of ca 1/3 of the population of all three countries which have an agricultural economy mostly supported by fishing and agriculture (tea and coffee plantations). The quality of the environment is therefore a fundamental factor in maintaining and increasing living standards of the growing population.

The main actual problem of this region is sustainable development, well-balanced between overusing of the natural resources and human economic well-being and progress. Essential factors in this problem are rate of population growth and dimensions of natural resources management.

Materials Used

The environmental GIS Project of the Victoria Lake region was based on processing and modelling following thematic data, both in raster and vector formats:

- Vector shape files of **administrative boundaries** (ArcGIS compatible format .shp), separately for Uganda, Tanzania and Kenya. Each .shp file has also additional supporting files like as .shx and .prj, which show additional information about projection and metadata.
- UNEP grids for the same spatial extent of Uganda, Tanzania and Kenya
- Raster **Precipitation climatic** data in text format, containing meteorological data in digital format: precipitation values in different months and years. The initial climatic data were in ASCII format which is text recording of the values of the annual precipitation for the whole Africa continent.
- Raster **Digital Elevation Models (DEMs)** showing relief characteristics and elevation of the research area. Data are taken from USGS website. 2 tiles of the USGS DEM map format (single file set of ASCII-encoded text containing numbers of coordinates and elevations) Initial Geographic reference was *WGS84*, projection - *Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area*, which is common for each DEM USGS tile. Both DEM tiles has auxiliary header files (.HDR) which contain information about byte order, number of rows, columns, number of bits, bands and other data. Files with extension .PRJ - E020N40.PRJ and E020S10.PRJ contain information about projection and its parameters. Files with extension **.STX** are statistics files which contain information about band parameters: number of bands, Min pixel value; Max pixel value; Mean pixel value and Standard Deviation.

- The metadata with geo-referencing information for the images is available in .prj files. There are two available data of GTopo30 - E020N40.DEM covering territory of Kenya and Uganda, and E020S10.DEM showing south-eastern part of Tanzania. DEM files contain horizontal grid spacing of 30 arc seconds (approximately 1 kilometre).
- Raster **Land Cover data** in raster format which is stored in .bsq format: IGBP.bsq. This file is a part of the global land cover characteristics database. The pixel values correspond to class numbers defined in the appropriate land cover classification scheme legend. Land Cover data projected in the Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area projection for the Africa land cover characteristics.
- Raster **Population data** were downloaded from the UNEP website. They contain raster data for the whole Africa continent. We have chosen data of population for two years for our research – 1990 and 2000 years. Each dataset had two different files – population density (popd00 and popd90 respectively) and population total.
- Additional, miscellaneous data set, containing **Landsat ETM+** images in MrSid format - S-36-00_2000.sid.

Methodology

Initial task of the data processing was entering data into the GIS Project based on ArcGIS, and organizing data in ArcCatalog. After entering data we made data management procedures using ArcToolbox in the ArcCatalog environment. During these steps we also performed spatial transformation of reference and projection of all the data, so that we could have uniform dataset for all layers. The raw data were modified to fit the needs of the GIS project. The following working steps show some of the stages involved in creating the final Project.

1. Administrative data preparation

The initial vector data were received from UNEP website. They are shapefiles covering both the whole region of interest and separately for each of the country - Tanzania, Kenya and Uganda. In spatial reference properties the *Africa Albers Equal Area* projection was defined for these files, which is the default main projection for the whole GIS Project.

Using the administrative data for the whole Region Of Interest (further ROI) a raster file was created using Vector to Raster conversion in Spatial Analyst. After that the new raster was re-classified in only one class with “1” value. This file was used for the clip operations with all other raster files reaching beyond the defined spatial extent. We name it as ROI file.

2. Climatic precipitation data conversion

Climatic data are initially available in ASCII text data format, which was converted to raster using ArcToolbox / Conversion Tools / To Raster / ASCII to Raster. After the conversion it was reprojected into *Africa Albers Equal Area Conic* projection using Projection tools. Initial dataset contained data for the whole Africa continent, so that it was clipped using ROI raster file to fit the working spatial extent.

3. DEM raster processing

For both files E020S10.DEM and E020N40.DEM the following spatial geographical reference system was defined, which is common for all layers of the GIS-project: *Africa Albers Equal Area Conic* projection with standard parallels 20 and -23, central meridian 25 and *Datum WGS-84*. CON function was used for highlighting pixels with high values and subtract 65536 from them, to receive negative values and to indicate water areas exactly. Both tiles of DEM file were merged into one. Then DEM area was clipped using ROI (Region Of Interest) raster mask containing one class with “1” values: Spatial Analysis / Raster Calculator / Raster Multiplication

4. Land Cover Map preparation and processing

For the Land Cover Map we needed first to create header file (.hdr) which contains technical information about map: № of bands, rows, columns, resolution, etc. After creation of header file and filling it out with necessary information, the band sequential raster file (.bsq file) could be previewed in the ArcCatalog. It contained data about Land Cover classes for the whole Africa continent. After that the file was imported to GRID raster ESRI format. In the new GRID file we

firstly defined spatial reference (WGS84) and then projected it to the *Albers Equal Area Conic* projection with standard parallels 20 / -23 and central meridian 25. New projected file was added to the GIS Project and clipped to the necessary spatial extent.

The next step in the Land Cover data processing was linking existing legend to the Raster file that we just added to the project. This legend is standardised, because the Land Cover map is a global land cover characteristics data base that was developed on a continent-by-continent basis and available on NASA data website. The description of the legend was available in the metadata and I copied this table with 16 classes (from 2nd to 17th) to the Excel text redactor. The file was converted to dBASE text file and added as a text table to the ArcGIS. Then the Attribute table of the Land Cover classes shapefile (Landuse.shp) was joined to this table using common column (*Value* for Landuse and *NI* for Legend). After the tables were linked, the legend description were made visible in the Table of Content of the ArcMap using Properties / Symbology function.

The third step in the Land Cover Map processing was re-classifying. The initial layer contained 16 classes which were too detailed for this research. Therefore, the Reclassification was done using Spatial Analyst / Reclassify function. I joined all kinds of forests into one class, “forests”, and different shrublands into one “shrubland” class. After the reclassification new raster contained 10 classes. The table with results of re-classification is given in the *Table 1*, Addendum

5. Population data processing

Projection of .twf data which initially had following geodetic reference system: *Projection GEOGRAPHIC, Spheroid CLARKE1866* into *Africa Albers Equal Area Conic* projection with standard parallels 20 and -23, central meridian 25 and *Datum WGS-84*. New data is in .tiff raster format. After that the projection, the data were clipped using ROI raster file.

Calculations of Population Statistics

Population for the Country and Provincial level was calculated using Zonal Statistics in Spatial Analyst. Results are listed in the *Table 7* and *Table 8*. The area statistics was calculated using Dissolve Manager in ArcToolbox. The necessary file (Adm_1) was dissolved so that we received the joined areas.

Kenya has 9 provinces. Maximal populated province – Nairobi: 1,933,500 in 2000, minimal – Lake Victoria: 143,162. Population density of Nairobi – 2695.66/ km²; population density of North Eastern – 8.37/ km². (Details in *Tables 7 and 8, Addendum*).

Uganda has 39 provinces. Maximal populated province (absolute) - Mpigi: 1,560,590, minimal – Kalangala: 5,028. Maximal population density is in Kampala – 2386.40/km²; minimal population density is in Kotido – 8.88/ km². (Details in *Tables 7 and 8, Addendum*).

Tanzania has 26 provinces. Maximal populated province in Tanzania – Dar-Es-Salaam: 1,858,020, minimal – Lake Victoria – 253,517. Maximal population density is again in Dar-Es-Salaam – 1762.46/ km²; minimal population density in Lake Victoria – 7,11/ km² (*Tables 7 and 8*).

To receive Population data for Provinces and Countries data I used *Spatial Analyst / Zonal Statistics* and used dissolved area of each country and population raster clipped for this country. To receive the area data, we used Add Field / Calculate Geometry / Square Kilometres. Areas of the countries are listed in the *Table 2*, Addendum.

Areas Calculations

The statistics of area in Tanzania, Kenya and Uganda are received from the layers “dissolved_countryname”. From the attribute table we received information about the size of each province as well as country. The results of population statistics for country level are in the *Table 3*, Addendum. The results of population statistics for provincial level of each country are in the *Tables 4 (Kenya), Table 5 (Uganda) and Table 6 (Tanzania)*, Addendum. Area statistics of the provinces within each country was calculated using *Zonal Statistics* function in *Spatial Analyst*. The detailed values of the area statistics are given in the *Tables 2*.

Rain Distribution

According to the layers' Overlay made using ArcMap and transparency function, the precipitation level is higher in the areas with middle precipitation (450-500mm), which is logical, because croplands cannot be located in too wet areas or in dry deserts with insufficient level of precipitation (see also Addendum, *Fig.7, Map of Correlation between Precipitation and Croplands area distribution*). Correlation between rain distribution and topography can be examined using Overlay of DEM relief raster layer and Precipitation GRID ESRI layer (*Fig.9, Map of Correlation between Precipitation and Heights Elevation in Victoria Lake area*). The most characteristic is high precipitation values in the valleys and above the lake, while very low levels in the highlands. Middle values are most probable in the plateau areas. Interesting dependence can be seen between Croplands spatial distribution and Topography: croplands are mostly located in the uplands and plateau, not in the valleys neither in highlands, *Fig. 8*, so that best location for the croplands is in the middle heights. After slicing DEM raster into 5 classes we received a statistics distribution of each elevation type in pixels: 56440 total, 11231 of class 1: 0-999 meters (19.8%); 13478 of class 2: 1000-1999 meters (23,8%); 26899 of class 3: 1999-3000 meter (47,6% of total), 4811 of class 4: 3000,1 -4000 meters (8.5%) and 21 of class 5: higher than 4000,1 meters (0.03%).

Issues

I. Estimate the total population in 2030

For the estimations of total population we used the following working steps:

- 1) Calculation the population growth rate:

$$\text{Growth Rate} = [(Population\ in\ 2000) - (Population\ in\ 1990)] / (Population\ in\ 1990)$$

- 2) Estimation the population in 2010 using population growth and the following formula:

$$[(Population\ in\ 2010 = (Population\ in\ 2000) + (Population\ in\ 2000) * Growth\ Rate)$$

- 3) Estimation the population in 2020 using population growth and the following formula:

$$[(Population\ in\ 2020 = (Population\ in\ 2010) + (Population\ in\ 2010) * Growth\ Rate)$$

- 4) Estimation the population in 2030 using population growth and the following formula:

$$[(Population\ in\ 2030 = (Population\ in\ 2020) + (Population\ in\ 2020) * Growth\ Rate)$$

II. How much cropland would be needed to feed the population in 2030 ?

To answer this question we need first estimate population in 2030 and then cropland needed.

Areas of cropland were estimated using statistics of the raster layer *Landcover*.

Amount of crop per capita was computed by dividing of the total cropland in each country (Tanzania, Kenya and Uganda) and their total population in each country respectively.

Total Cropland needed in 2030 was estimated by multiplying of the crop per capita needed for the population and the total population in 2030. The main results are listed in the *Table 11* (Addendum).

III. What % of the total forest area has to be converted to cropland to expand cropland in 2030?

To estimate % of the total forest area has to be converted to cropland first total forest area per country was calculated using raster statistics for the *Landcover* layer. As we know how much cropland there is in each country now, and how much is needed in 2030, we estimated increase in cropland that is necessary for the 2030 by distraction from one another. After that we distracted amount of forest areas that has to be converted to necessary cropland plantations and we received the negative values, because there are more need for croplands than forest areas available. To receive the percentage we calculated the received negative values of areas needed as a percentage from the actual areas taken the last ones for 100 %. The results are listed in *Table 12*, Addendum.

IV. How much forest can be converted to cropland from protected areas in each country ?

To calculate areas of forest that may be converted to croplands I firstly added shapefile "Protect_areas.shp" from Geodatabase to the ArcMap. Then new layer was clipped using mask of Region Of Interest. After that clipped vector layer was converted to raster using Spatial Analyst / vector to Raster. New raster re-classified to only one class containing 1 value. Then I used Raster

Calculator to multiply Land Cover (reclassified) raster layer to the new raster layer of protected areas. After calculation I received the raster of Land Cover only for the territory of protected area zones (Fig.16). From the attribute table of this new raster we can see the values in pixels for the area of forests and other land cover classes. According to the results of the statistics, the total area of forests in protected zones that has to be converted to cropland is 1049 km².

To receive these areas for each country separately, I used raster layer for each country separately (previously re-classed to 1 class only with value 1) and Raster Calculator from Spatial Analysis.

The area of forests located in the territory of protected zones that has to be converted to cropland for Tanzania is 1025 km². The area of forests located in the territory of protected zones that has to be converted to cropland for Uganda is 15 km². The area of forests located in the territory of protected zones that has to be converted to cropland for Kenya is 9 km².

To receive areas outside the protected zones I firstly used Raster Calculator to create raster layers of all Land Cover areas for each country. Then I subtracted the areas located in protected zones from the total one for each country respectively and received final results for outside protected areas: for Tanzania – 7509-1025=6484 km², for Uganda -257-15=242 km² and for Kenya –804-9=795 km².

Main Results

1. Total Population of countries in 2030:
Kenya – 67,032,221; Tanzania – 86,375,938; Uganda - 44,202,232.
2. To feed population in 2030 the following areas of cropland would be needed in 2030:
Kenya – 248,778 km²; Tanzania – 991,469 km²; Uganda - 153,992 km².
3. From the total forest area the following percentage has to be converted to cropland in 2030:
Kenya – 370%; Tanzania – 148%; Uganda - 618%.
The needs for the cropland exceed the existing areas of forests available!
4. From the area of protected zones the following amount of forests can be converted to cropland inside and outside protected areas:
Inside protected areas: Kenya – 9km²; Tanzania –1025 km²; Uganda - 15km².
Outside protected areas: Kenya – 795km²; Tanzania – 6484km²; Uganda - 242km².

Conclusion

According to the results, the population keeps growing and the demand for the natural resources for the feeding of population will remain high. The country with maximal amount of population is now and will be Tanzania, reaching more than 86 mln people by 2030. This country will therefore have maximal demand for natural resources and the government of this country should take special care of the sustainable development of its resources and region. However, some special concern may increase in case of Uganda which has maximal potential area of forests to be converted to the croplands, because having still great absolute number of total population (more than 44 mln people) it has much less variable and diverse natural resources, especially forests. When examining the forests that have to be converted from the inside and outside the protected areas, Tanzania has the most vulnerable situation, in impressive absolute value (more than 6 thousands km²) as well as in “quality” proportion: 1/6 of the total forests are located in protected areas.

Therefore, the politics of sustainable development is an absolute prerequisite for successful environmental monitoring in the Victoria Lake region. It is necessary to find out ways for sustainable using of natural resources and to maintain economic reasonable development of all three countries, and thus to provide harmonic coexistence of the humans and nature.

I would strongly suggest switching from the extensive using of fishery as the main way of economic development towards less ecology-pressing styles of life and economic model: e.g. development of the resource-saving technologies or artificial planting of new forests areas.

ADDENDUM (Tables, Maps and Graphs)

Table 1. Re-Classification of land Cover Classes in Lake Victoria area

<i>Land Class Name</i>	<i>New Land Class Name</i>
Evergreen Broadleaf Forest	Forest
Deciduous Needleleaf Forest	
Deciduous Broadleaf Forest	
Mixed Forest	
Closed Shrublands	Shrublands
Open Shrublands	
Woody Savannas	Savannas
Savannas	
Grasslands	Grasslands
Permanent Wetlands	Permanent Wetlands
Croplands	Croplands
Urban and Built-Up	Urban and Built-Up
Cropland/Natural Vegetation Mosaic	Cropland/Natural Vegetation Mosaic
Snow and Ice	Snow and Ice
Barren or Sparsely Vegetated	Barren or Sparsely Vegetated
Water Bodies	Water Bodies

Table 2. Total areas of Countries

Country Name	Total Area, km ²
Kenya	592,482 km ²
Tanzania	942,852 km ²
Uganda	240,977 km ²

Table 3. Population Statistics at Country level:

Country Name	Population-1990	Population-2000
Kenya	24,181,700	31,231,500
Tanzania	27,037,200	36,140,900
Uganda	17,997,800	24,316,500

Table 4. Population Statistics at Provincial level, Kenya:

1990				2000		
Provinces	Area, km ²	Total Population	Population Density	Area, km ²	Total Population	Population Density
CENTRAL	13,064.29	3,568,300	273.13	13,064.29	4,153,580	317.93
COAST	83,821.93	1,969,410	23.50	83,821.93	2,593,070	30.94
EASTERN	157,189.02	4,163,680	26.49	157,189.02	4,962,130	31.57
L Victoria	3,569.63	118,853	33.30	3,569.63	143,162	40.11
N. EASTERN	126,447.08	508,264	4.02	126,447.08	1,057,840	8.37
NAIROBI	717.26	1,237,950	1725.93	717.26	1,933,500	2695.66
NYANZA	12,869.70	3,909,410	303.77	12,869.70	4,774,300	370.97
RIFT VALLEY	175,837.18	5,686,540	32.34	175,837.18	7,824,280	44.50
WESTERN	8,648.34	3,019,330	349.12	8,648.34	3,789,640	438.19

Table 5. Population Statistics at Provincial level, Uganda:

1990				2000		
Provinces	Area, km ²	Tot. Population	Pop. Density	Area, km ²	Total Population	Pop. Density
Apac	6,240.38	453,483	72.67	6,240.38	664,639	106.51
Arua	8,171.84	690,673	84.52	8,171.84	947,217	115.91
Bundibugyo	2,067.73	139,096	67.27	2,067.73	181,567	87.81
Bushenyi	5,380.41	793,922	147.56	5,380.41	1,133,840	210.73
Gulu	11,699.94	386,286	33.02	11,699.94	480,929	41.11
Hoima	5,807.39	213,396	36.75	5,807.39	272,628	46.94
Iganga	4,844.83	929,568	191.87	4,844.83	1,313,950	271.21
Jinja	808.97	266,250	329.12	808.97	348,613	430.94
Kabale	1,724.55	449,359	260.57	1,724.55	584,236	338.78
Kabarole	8,873.15	909,504	102.50	8,873.15	1,265,310	142.60
Kalangala	476.03	3,557	7.47	476.03	5,028	10.56
Kampala	295.52	486,012	1644.61	295.52	705,225	2386.40
Kamuli	4,207.49	525,900	124.99	4,207.49	745,774	177.25
Kapchorwa	1,682.49	117,098	69.60	1,682.49	174,200	103.54
Kasese	2,941.66	316,565	107.61	2,941.66	440,266	149.67
Kibaale	4,849.37	234,573	48.37	4,849.37	299,491	61.76
Kiboga	3,938.43	141,624	35.96	3,938.43	155,687	39.53
Kisoro	765.88	198,317	258.94	765.88	290,392	379.16
Kitgum	16,623.53	391,532	23.55	16,623.53	461,337	27.75
Kotido	13,073.55	138,613	10.60	13,073.55	116,051	8.88
Kumi	2,879.69	273,814	95.08	2,879.69	288,326	100.12
Lake Victoria	28,655.33	292,355	10.20	28,655.33	419,594	14.64
Lira	7,479.19	589,329	78.80	7,479.19	806,912	107.89
Luwero	9,207.49	534,804	58.08	9,207.49	649,901	70.58
Masaka	5,538.79	830,102	149.87	5,538.79	1,204,860	217.53
Masindi	9,748.05	293,170	30.07	9,748.05	352,891	36.20
Mbale	2,489.18	808,018	324.61	2,489.18	1,079,450	433.66
Mbarara	10,647.77	950,581	89.28	10,647.77	1,355,710	127.32
Moroto	15,016.16	174,877	11.65	15,016.16	146,563	9.76
Moyo	4,816.74	150,755	31.30	4,816.74	212,762	44.17
Mpigi	4,659.91	1,077,890	231.31	4,659.91	1,560,590	334.90
Mubende	6,440.39	606,737	94.21	6,440.39	831,556	129.12
Mukono	5,076.91	917,918	180.80	5,076.91	1,289,390	253.97
Nebbi	3,069.03	315,574	102.83	3,069.03	430,973	140.43
Pallisa	1,967.46	399,683	203.15	1,967.46	554,020	281.59
Rakai	3,904.87	399,600	102.33	3,904.87	579,770	148.47
Rukungiri	3,202.56	507,856	158.58	3,202.56	677,416	211.52
Soroti	9,539.53	456,751	47.88	9,539.53	428,475	44.92
Tororo	2,465.88	632,703	256.58	2,465.88	860,984	349.16

Table 6. Population Statistics at Provincial level, Tanzania:

1990				2000		
Provinces	Area, km ²	Total Population	Population Density	Area, km ²	Total Population	Population Density
Arusha	85,211.24	1,719,930	20.18	85,211.24	2,519,570	29.57
Dar-Es-Salaam	1,054.22	1,208,000	1145.87	1,054.22	1,858,020	1762.46
Dodoma	41,238.76	1,438,030	34.87	41,238.76	1,807,880	43.84
Iringa	55,810.17	1,402,140	25.12	55,810.17	1,611,440	28.87
Kagera	29,268.43	1,596,160	54.54	29,268.43	2,185,060	74.66
Kaskazini-Pemba	536.49	140,079	261.10	536.49	173,623	323.63
Kaskazini-Unguja	561.24	128,478	228.92	561.24	165,152	294.26
Kigoma	47,276.14	988,413	20.91	47,276.14	1,645,940	34.82
Kilimanjaro	12,535.95	1,243,930	99.23	12,535.95	1,452,960	115.90
Kusini Unguja	835.26	83,702	100.21	835.26	86,007	102.97
Kusini-Pemba	433.83	119,969	276.53	433.83	150,952	347.95
L. Victoria	35,644.71	180,002	5.05	35,644.71	253,517	7.11
Lindi	66,010.32	753,210	11.41	66,010.32	851,351	12.90
Mara	21,895.81	1,143,960	52.25	21,895.81	1,458,550	66.61
Mbeya	61,414.28	1,725,640	28.10	61,414.28	2,170,210	35.34
Mjini-Magharibi	189.39	194,282	1025.81	189.39	239,527	1264.70
Morogoro	70,925.72	1,428,140	20.14	70,925.72	1,857,410	26.19
Mtwara	17,878.77	997,343	55.78	17,878.77	1,189,240	66.52
Mwanza	18,015.43	1,964,490	109.04	18,015.43	2,980,740	165.45
Pwani	33,239.07	1,177,950	35.44	33,239.07	1,619,820	48.73
Rukwa	75,148.77	841,190	11.19	75,148.77	1,189,840	15.83
Ruvuma	63,620.22	908,468	14.28	63,620.22	1,160,240	18.24
Shinyanga	51,372.45	2,016,910	39.26	51,372.45	2,781,460	54.14
Singida	50,411.60	941,872	18.68	50,411.60	1,185,340	23.51
Tabora	74,440.38	1,226,100	16.47	74,440.38	1,798,380	24.16
Tanga	26,788.75	1,468,830	54.83	26,788.75	1,748,650	65.28

Table 7. Maximum populated provinces for each country (absolute figures and per area unit)

1990				2000		
Country	Province	Absolute Values	Per area unit	Province	Absolute Values	Per area unit
Kenya	Rift Valley	5,686,540	32.34	Rift Valley	7,824,280	44.50
Kenya	Nairobi	1,237,950	1725.93	Nairobi	1,933,500	2695.66
Tanzania	Shinyanga	2,016,910	39.26	Mwanza	2,980,740	165.45
Tanzania	Dar-Es-Salaam	1145.87	1,054.22	Dar-Es-Salaam	1,858,020	1762.46
Uganda	Mpigi	1,077,890	231.31	Mpigi	1,560,590	334.90
Uganda	Kampala	486,012	1644.61	Kampala	705,225	2386.40

Table 8. Minimum populated province for each country (absolute figures and per area unit)

1990				2000		
Country	Province	Absolute Values	Per area unit	Province	Absolute Values	Per area unit
Kenya	L Victoria	118,853	33.30	L Victoria	143,162	40.11
Kenya	N. Eastern	508,264	4.02	N. Eastern	1,057,840	8.37
Tanzania	Kusini Unguja	83,702	100.21	Kusini Unguja	86,007	102.97
Tanzania	L. Victoria	180,002	5.05	L. Victoria	253,517	7.11
Uganda	Kalangala	3,557	7.47	Kalangala	5,028	10.56
Uganda	Kalangala	3,557	7.47	Kotido	116,051	8.88

Table 9. The largest population increase rate per provinces (absolute values and % of change)

1990				2000	
Country	Province	Total Population 1990	Total Population 2000	Increase in absolute values	Increase in %
Kenya	N. Eastern	508,264	1,057,840	549,576	108.13
Kenya	Rift Valley	5,686,540	7,824,280	2,137,740	37.59
Tanzania	Kigoma	988,413	1,645,940	657,527	66.52
Tanzania	Mwanza	1,964,490	2,980,740	1,016,250	51.73
Uganda	Kapchorwa	117,098	174,200	57,102	48.76
Uganda	Mpigi	1,077,890	1,560,590	482,700	44.78

Table 10. Area of cropland within each country

Country Name	Area of Cropland
Kenya	115,910 km ²
Tanzania	363,191 km ²
Uganda	84,714 km ²

Table 11. Computations of Population in 2030 and total cropland needed in 2030

Country	Population in 2000	Area of cropland	Crop per capita	Population in 2030	Total cropland needed in 2030
Kenya	31,231,500	115,910	0.003711317	67,032,221	248,778
Tanzania	31,640,900	363,191	0.011478529	86,375,938	991,469
Uganda	24,316,500	84,714	0.003483807	44,202,232	153,992

Table 12. Estimations the Forest areas that have to be converted to Croplands for 2030.

Country	Increase in cropland from 2000 to 2030	Total forest area per country	Area of forest that has to be converted	Area of forest that has to be converted (%)
Kenya	132,868	28,279	-104,589	370
Tanzania	628,278	252,755	-375,523	148
Uganda	69,278	9,651	-59,627	618

Fig.1 Elevation (relief) Map

Fig.2. Precipitation Map

Fig.3. Land Classes Map, reclassified to 10 classes

Fig.4 Land Classes Map, 16 classes

Fig.5. Map of Population in 2000

Fig.6 Cropland areas in Tanzania

Fig.7. Cropland areas in Uganda

Fig.8 Cropland areas in Kenya

Fig.9. Correlation of spatial distribution of cropland areas and precipitation

Fig.10. Correlation of spatial distribution of cropland areas and topography

Fig.11. Correlation of spatial distribution of cropland areas and precipitation

Fig.12. Topography sliced in 5 classes

Fig.13. Kenya Zonal population statistics for Administrative provinces

Fig.14. Uganda Zonal population statistics for Administrative provinces

Fig.15. Tanzania Zonal population statistics for Administrative provinces

Fig.16. Land Classes in Protected areas

MATERIALS USED:

- Shape files of **administrative boundaries** (ArcGIS compatible format .shp), separately for Uganda, Tanzania and Kenya. Each .shp file has also additional supporting files like as .shx and .prj, which show additional information about projection and metadata. UNEP grids for the same spatial extent of Uganda, Tanzania and Kenya
- **Precipitation climatic** data in text format, containing meteorological data in digital format: precipitation values in different months and years. The initial climatic data were in ASCII format which is text recording of the values of the annual precipitation for the whole Africa continent.
- **Digital Elevation Models (DEMs)** showing relief characteristics and elevation of the research area. Data are taken from USGS website. 2 tiles of the USGS DEM map format (single file set of ASCII-encoded text containing numbers of coordinates and elevations) Initial Geographic reference was *WGS84*, projection - *Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area*, which is common for each DEM USGS tile. The metadata with geo-referencing information for the images is available in .prj files. There are two available data of GTopo30 - E020N40.DEM covering territory of Kenya and Uganda, and E020S10.DEM showing south-eastern part of Tanzania. DEM files contain horizontal grid spacing of 30 arc seconds (approximately 1 kilometre).
- **Land Cover data** in raster format which is stored in .bsq format: IGBP.bsq. This file is a part of the global land cover characteristics database. The pixel values correspond to class numbers defined in the appropriate land cover classification scheme legend. Land Cover data projected in the Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area projection for the Africa land cover characteristics.
- **Population data** were downloaded from the UNEP website. They contain raster data for the whole Africa continent. We have chosen data of population for two years for our research – 1990 and 2000 years. Each dataset had two different files – population density (popd00 and popd90 respectively) and population total.
- **ArcGIS Desktop Help 9.2.** On-line Guidebook and Tutorial, <http://webhelp.esri.com/arcgisdesktop/9.2/index.cfm?TopicName=welcome>
- **Longley, P A, Goodchild M F, Maguire D J and Rhind D W. 2005. Geographical Information Systems and Science.** Wiley, 2005.
Chapter 5: Georeferencing (p.p.109-123),
Chapter 9: GIS Data Collection (p.p.199-217),
Chapter 10: Creating and Maintaining Geographic Databases (p.p.217-239)